

Skeneid gastropods (Vetigastropoda, Trochoidea) from the continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Gasterópodos Skeneidos (Vetigastropoda, Trochoidea) de la plataforma continental y talud frente a Galicia (NO Península Ibérica)

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ABSTRACT

Among the material obtained in several expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain) 128 shells of species assigned to family Skeneidae were found, 47 of them with soft parts. They belong to 11 species in 8 genera (*Skenea*, *Dikoleps*, *Cirsonella*, *Ganesa*, *Mikro*, *Lissomphalia*, *Parviturbo*, *Seamountiella*). *Skenea serpuloides* and *Dikoleps nitens* were found only in the shelf samples, *Cirsonella romettensis* were collected in a wide bathymetric range, from the shelf bottoms to 2033 m depth, and the remaining species have been collected only in samples of the slope in the depth range 400-1500 m. The most abundant species were *Cirsonella romettensis* and *Seamountiella azorica*.

RESUMEN

Entre el material obtenido en varias expediciones a lo largo de la plataforma y talud continental de Galicia (NO de España) se encontraron 128 conchas de especies asignadas a la familia Skeneidae, 47 de ellas con partes blandas. Pertenecen a 11 especies en 8 géneros (*Skenea*, *Dikoleps*, *Cirsonella*, *Ganesa*, *Mikro*, *Lissomphalia*, *Parviturbo*, *Seamountiella*). *Skenea serpuloides* y *Dikoleps nitens* se encontraron solo en las muestras de la plataforma, *Cirsonella romettensis* se recolectó en un amplio rango batimétrico, desde la plataforma hasta los 2033 m de profundidad, y las especies restantes se recolectaron solo en muestras de la pendiente en el rango de profundidad 400 -1500 m. Las especies más abundantes fueron *Cirsonella romettensis* y *Seamountiella azorica*.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, northeast Atlantic, taxonomy, *Skenea*, *Dikoleps*, *Cirsonella*, *Ganesa*, *Mikro*, *Lissomphalia*, *Parviturbo*, *Seamountiella*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Atlántico noreste, taxonomía, *Skenea*, *Dikoleps*, *Cirsonella*, *Ganesa*, *Mikro*, *Lissomphalia*, *Parviturbo*, *Seamountiella*.

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INTRODUCTION

The present work continues the study of the gastropods collected during a series of expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain) between 2002 and 2009, carried out by the Marine Biology Station of A Graña (belonging to Santiago de Compostela University). Previous papers addressed conoidean, rissoidean, and seguenzioidean gastropods from these expeditions (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022a, 2022b, 2023). This paper deals with the species of Skeneidae.

The so-called “skeneimorphs” comprise a polyphyletic assemblage of minute gastropods belonging to phylogenetically distant clades of Vetigastropoda (Scissurelloidea, Seguenzioidea and Trochoidea), Neomphalida or Heterobranchia (HEB *ET AL.*, 2008; KANO, 2008; KANO *ET AL.* 2009; KUNZE *ET AL.*, 2008, 2016; HASZPRUNAR *ET AL.*, 2011, 2020; HICKMAN, 2013; NYE *ET AL.*, 2013). To overcome the ‘catch-all’ concept of ‘skeneimorph’ gastropods, HASZPRUNAR *ET AL.* (2016) restricted Skeneidae s.s. to those species forming a monophyletic group including the type species, *Skenea serpuloides* (Montagu, 1808), and supported by morphological synapomorphies as well as by molecular studies. However, many of the genera that are still assigned to Skeneidae (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023) are pending their anatomical and molecular study to ratify their correct inclusion in this family.

Skeneids occur in a wide variety of habitats, from intertidal or shallow coastal waters down to the deep bottoms, including hydrothermal vents and some of them are associated with various organic remains (sunken wood, algal holdfasts, whale bones) (MARSHALL 1988; WARÉN AND BOUCHET, 1993, 2001, HASEGAWA 1997; OKUTANI *ET AL.*, 2000; KUNZE 2011; HASZPRUNAR *ET AL.*, 2016).

The northeastern Atlantic Skeneidae have been the subject of several studies in recent decades (i.e. WARÉN, 1992,

1993, 1996; RUBIO *ET AL.*, 1998, 2004, 2015, 2019; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2008, 2010, 2020; RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2013a, 2013b). In the present work we include the species belonging to the following genera currently assigned to the family Skeneidae (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023): *Skenea*, *Dikoleps*, *Cirsonella*, *Ganesa*, *Mikro*, *Lissomphalia*, *Parviturbo* and *Seamountiella*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied proceeds from different expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain) in the depth range 110-3200 m. Data on these expeditions are provided in the previous papers by OLIVER *ET AL.* (2022a, 2022b, 2023). Sampling methodology and processing of samples were described by PARAPAR & MOREIRA (2009) and in the abovementioned papers.

Benthic samples were taken by means of the following gears: Naturalist Dredge (DRN), Agassiz trawl (AT), Rock dredge (DRR) and Epibenthic sledge (EBS). Samples obtained were sieved and specimens were fixed with ethanol 70% neutralized with borax. Animals retained in sieves of ≥ 2 mm were sorted to high taxonomic levels on the Marine Biological Station of A Graña (University of Santiago de Compostela).

The entire collection of 128 shells and specimens from the samples studied have been deposited (preserved dry and in 70% ethanol respectively) at the Museo de Historia Natural of the Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Galicia (Spain), with the deposit number: MHN-USC-25219.

The following abbreviations have been used:

juv: juvenile
sh: empty shell
spc: shell with soft parts

Expeditions:

DAI/02: DIVA-Artabria I (2002)
DAI/03: DIVA-Artabria I (2003)
VE/04: Vertidos (2004)
DAII/08: DIVA-Artabria II (2008)
SE/08: A Selva (2008)
DAII/09: DIVA-Artabria II (2009)

RESULTS

In the samples studied a total of 128 shells (47 of them collected alive) were found, in the depth range 110-2033 m, belonging to 11 species (one of them identified with doubts) in 8 genera that are related below.

SYSTEMATICS

Superfamily TROCHOIDEA

Family SKENEIDAE

Genus *Skenea* J. Fleming, 1825

Type species: *Helix serpuloides* Montagu, 1808

Skenea serpuloides (Montagu, 1808) (Fig. 1)

Helix serpuloides Montagu 1808: 147, pl. 21, fig. 3.

Delphinula laevis Philippi, 1844: 146, t 25 fig.2.

Skenea divisa Forbes & Hanley: 161, t. 74, figs. 4-6.

Skenea serpuloides (Montagu, 1808) – RODRÍGUEZ-BABIO & THIRIOT-QUIEVREUX (1976: 526, pl. 4 figs. A-B); FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977: 81-83, figs. 60-61); AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1984: 11, fig. 36); RUBIO-SALAZAR (1991: 188-190, figs. 1, 3: 1-4); WARÉN (1991: figs. 2C-D, 8C-D); WARÉN (1992: figs. 4B, 5A, 6A); RUBIO & ROLÁN (2013b: 87-91, figs. 1-3).

Material examined: Three empty shells in the same sample at 110-111 m. SPAIN • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 08°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 08°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VE/04 GA-AT-110.

Type locality: Devon, England.

This is the type species of the genus. It is a common sublittoral species down to 150 m, known from the British Islands to Morocco, Canaries and the Mediterranean, frequently associated to coarse detritic bottoms with calcareous algae (FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1977; RUBIO-SALAZAR, 1991, 2011). A drawing

of the animal was provided by RUBIO-SALAZAR (1991: 189, fig. 1), and SEM photographs of the critical point dried animal by RUBIO & ROLÁN (2013b). HASZPRUNAR *ET AL.* (2016) provide a detailed anatomical description based on serial semi-thin sectioning and 3D reconstructions.

Skenea basistriata (Jeffreys, 1877) (Fig. 2A-G)

Cyclostrema basistriatum Jeffreys, 1877: 303.

Skenea basistriata (Jeffreys) – FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977: 91-93, figs. 69-70); WARÉN (1991: 64-65, figs. 5A-B, F, H, 7A, C); WARÉN (1993: 176-178, figs. 16A-F, 17A-D).

Material examined: Three shells, one of them with soft parts (Fig. 2), in two samples within the depth range 598-1499 m depth. SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 42°45.9'N, 09°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Type locality: Lofoten, northern Norway.

Figure 1. *Skenea serpuloides* (VE/04 GA-AT-110). A: shell (1.45 x 0.83 mm); B: umbilical area; C: apical view of the other shell (1.1 mm in diameter); D: protoconch.

Figura 1. *Skenea serpuloides* (VE/04 GA-AT-110). A: concha (1,45 x 0,83 mm); B: área umbilical; C: vista apical de otra concha (1,1 mm de diámetro); D: protoconcha.

According to WARÉN (1993), *S. basistriata* is a polymorphic species. The specimens studied fall within the variability of the species. It is a common

species widely distributed from northern Siberia to the Bay of Biscay and off Portugal in the depth range 90-2500 m (WARÉN, 1993).

Genus *Dikoleps* Høisæter, 1968

Type species: *Margarita pusilla* Jeffreys, 1847, accepted as *Dikoleps nitens* (Philippi, 1844).

Dikoleps nitens (Philippi, 1844) (Fig. 2H-K)

Delphinula nitens Philippi, 1844: 146, pl. 25, fig. 4.

Margarita pusilla Jeffreys, 1847: 17.

Cyclostrema nitens (Philippi) – JEFFREYS (1865: 289).

Dikoleps pusilla (Jeffreys) – HØISÆTER (1968: 48).

Skenea nitens (Philippi) – FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977: 84-85, figs. 62-63)

Dikoleps nitens (Philippi) – RUBIO-SALAZAR (1991: 191-193, figs. 2, 4, 7B, 14-16); WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993: 27, fig. 21D-F); RUBIO ET AL. (2004: 116-120, figs. 1-13).

Material examined: Three empty shells in the same sample at 233-237 m. SPAIN • 3 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43°59.621'N, 08°14.285'W; 233-237 m; 16 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-20.

Type locality: Fossil, Carrubbare near Reggio di Calabria, Italy.

Figure 2. A-G. *Skenea basistriata* (DAII/08-EBS-27). A: shell with soft parts (1.9 mm); B-C: different views of the protoconch; D: protoconch/teleoconch transition; E: operculum; F: umbilical area; G: umbilical view of an empty shell from the same sample. H-K. *Dikoleps nitens* (SE/08 EBS-20). H: shell (0.73 x 0.90 mm); I: umbilical area; J: growth lines; K: protoconch.

Figura 2. A-G. *Skenea basistriata* (DAII/08-EBS-27). A: concha con partes blandas (1,9 mm); B-C: diferentes vistas de la protoconcha; D: transición protoconcha/teleoconcha; E: opérculo; F: área umbilical; G: vista umbilical de una concha vacía de la misma muestra. H-K. *Dikoleps nitens* (SE/08 EBS-20). H: concha (0,73 x 0,90 mm); I: área umbilical; J: líneas de crecimiento; K: protoconcha.

This is a common subtidal species, normally associated with “maerl” bottoms distributed from Norway HØISÆTER (1968) to the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula (FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1977; RUBIO-SALAZAR, 1991;

RUBIO ET AL. 2004). A drawing of the animal was provided by RUBIO-SALAZAR (1991: 192, fig. 2), and SEM photographs of the critical-point dried animal by WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993), and RUBIO ET AL. (2004: 119, figs. 8-13).

Genus *Cirsonella* Angas, 1877

Type species: *Cirsonella australis* Angas, 1877 accepted as *Cirsonella weldii* (Tenison Woods, 1877).

Cirsonella romettensis (Granata Grillo, 1877) (Figs. 3A-H; 4A, B)

Oxystele romettensis Granata Grillo, 1877: 5.

Cirsonella romettensis (Granata Grillo) – WARÉN (1992: 160, figs 4C, 9E, 11C-E, 12a).

Material examined: Forty-three shells (16 with soft parts) in fourteen samples between 230 and 2033 m. SPAIN • 2 spc; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 3 spc; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DIVA ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 1 spc; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 3 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 3 spc + 11 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 8 spc; 44°09.896'N, 08°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 08°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 18 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11 • 1 sh; 43° 33.20'N, 08°58.78'W to 43°34.57'N, 08°56.90'W; 230-236 m; 16 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-01 • 3 sh; 43°32.5'N, 09°25.37'W to 43°33.6'N, 09° 24.5'W; 848-1027 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-05 • 1 sh; 43°24.63'N, 09°31.55'W to 43°25.67'N, 09°30.73'W; 880-827 m; 20 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-08. • 1 sh; 43°20.49'N, 09°34.03'W to 43°21.22'N, 09°32.96'W; 846-771 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-16 • 1 sh (juv); 43°19.92'N, 09°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 09°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15. • 1 spc; 43°23.22'N; 09°32.30'W to 43°42.28'N; 09°30.83' W; 773-862 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-31 • 3 sh; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709-728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-25. • 1 sh; 42°27.66'N, 09°46.13'W to 42°29.08'N, 09°45.31'W; 2033-2091 m; 30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-29.

Type locality: Pliocene-Pleistocene and Recent, Strait of Messina, Italy.

This is a common species from the Bay of Biscay south to off West Africa and the Mediterranean, in the 100-2300 depth range (WARÉN, 1992; SYSOEV, 2014). HOFFMAN ET AL. (2010) recorded one shell further north in Rockall Bank at 1087 m. GOFAS ET AL. (2021) recorded

one living specimen and three shells on Galicia Bank at 1000-1500 m. According to NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) it is a stenobathic species living on small hard substrates mainly in the 100-1000 m depth interval, often associated with the living brachiopods *Gryphus vitreus*.

Cirsonella aff. *gaudryi* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 3I-K)

Tharsis gaudryi Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 486, pl. 21 figs 13-15.

Cirsonella gaudryi Dautzenberg & H. Fischer – MARTINS ET AL. (2009: 58, fig. 30); HOFFMAN ET AL. (2010: 51; 2020: 56-58, fig. 49).

Material examined: Only one eroded shell at 908-1106 m. SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Type locality: off the Azores, 1385 m.

Figure 3. A-H. *Cirsonella romettensis*. A, B: shell with soft parts (1.8×1.9 mm) and detail of the operculum (SE/08 DRN-11); C: juvenile shell (0.8×1.0 mm) (DAI/02 AT-1000); D: umbilical area; E, F: lateral view of its protoconch and detail of its microsculpture; G, H: protoconch of another shell (SE/08 DRN-7) and detail of its microsculpture. I-K. *Cirsonella* aff. *gaudryi*. I: eroded shell (1.5×1.6 mm) (SE/08)-DRN7); J: protoconch; K: umbilical area.

Figura 4. *Cirsonella romettensis*. A, B: concha (1.8×1.9 mm) y detalle del opérculo (SE/08 DRN-11); C: concha juvenil ($0,8 \times 1,0$ mm) (DAI/02 AT-1000); D: área umbilical; E, F: vista lateral de su protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura; G, H: protoconcha de otra concha (SE/08 DRN-7) y detalle de su microescultura. I-K. *Cirsonella* aff. *gaudryi*. I: concha erosionada ($1,5 \times 1,6$ mm) (SE/08)-DRN7); J: protoconcha; K: zona umbilical.

The eroded shell collected at A SELVA fishing area resembles *Cirsonella gaudryi*, but that species has a wider umbilicus without cordlets. It is known from Hatton Bank (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010), the

Azores (DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896; MARTINS *ET AL.*, 2009), the South Azorean Seamount Chain (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020) and west of Morocco (DAUTZENBERG, 1927) in the depth range 117-1500 m.

Genus *Seamountiella* Rubio, Gofas & Rolán, 2019

Type species: *Tinostoma azoricum* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896.

Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 4C-E; 5)

Tinostoma azoricum Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 485, pl. 21, figs. 16-18.

Tinostoma azoricum (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer) – BECK *ET AL.* (2006: 70); HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2011: 39, figs. 76-78).

Seamountiella azorica (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer) – RUBIO *ET AL.* (2019: 253-258, figs. 1-4).

Material examined: Forty one shells (26 with soft parts) in 5 samples from 417-1286 m. SPAIN • 2 spc (juv); polygon delimited by points 44°10.00'N, 09°00.00'W / 44°10.00'N, 08°35.00'W / 44°00.00'N; 09°00.00'W / 44°07.00'N; 08°35.00'W; 417-668 m; 27 Jul. 2007; SARRIDAL (07) SARRI-4 • 23 spc + 9 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 4 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 43°19.92'N, 09°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 09°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15 • 1 sh; 43°23.22'N; 09°32,30'W to 43°42.28'N; 09°30.83' W; 773-862 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-31 • 1 spc; 42°46.56'N; 11°51.61'W to 42°47.23'N; 11°51.19' W; 960-965 m; 18 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRR-92.

Type locality: Azores, Pr. Alice, st.46, 1385 m, st. 117, 2102 m

The generic allocation of this species was revised by RUBIO *ET AL.* (2019), who provided a detailed description and a drawing of the animal. It is a common species widely distributed on the NE

Atlantic seamounts and banks in the depth range 470-4060 m (BECK *ET AL.*, 2006; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011, 2020; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017; RUBIO *ET AL.*, 2019; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021).

Genus *Ganesa* Jeffreys, 1883

Type species: *Ganesa nitidiuscula* Jeffreys, 1883, subsequent designation by Bush (1897).

Ganesa nitidiuscula Jeffreys, 1883 (Fig. 6)

Ganesa nitidiuscula Jeffreys, 1883: 94, pl. xIx fig. 8.

Ganesa nitidiuscula Jeffreys – WARÉN (1980: 17); WARÉN (1992: 176, fig. 33B).

Material examined: Two empty shells (one of them eroded) in two samples, depth range 908-1286 m. SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh (juv); 43°19.92'N, 09°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 09°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15.

Type locality: According to HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2018) two locations were mentioned by JEFFREYS (1883): Porcupine 1869/23a, 56°13'N -14°18'W (Rockall Bank, 420 fathoms) and Porcupine 1870/17, 39°42'N - 09°43'W (off W Portugal, 600-1095 fathoms).

This species is known from the Faroes to Mauritania, including the

South Azorean Seamount Chain, in the NE Atlantic, and on the Bahamas Bank,

Figure 4. A, B. *Cirsonella romettensis* (DAI/03 EBS-800) (approximate size 2.5 mm). C-E. *Seamountiella azorica* (DAII/09 DRR-92); live specimens (approximate size 4 mm) in which the soft parts with eggs can be seen by transparency.

Figura 4. A, B. *Cirsonella romettensis* (DAI/03 EBS-800) (tamaño aproximado 2,5 mm). C-E. *Seamountiella azorica* (DAII/09 DRR-92); ejemplares vivos (tamaño aproximado 4 mm) en los que se pueden ver por transparencia las partes blandas con huevos.

in the NW Atlantic, in the depth range 474–2000 m (JEFFREYS, 1883; HOFFMAN

ET AL., 2018, 2020). Here it is recorded for the first time in Spanish waters.

Genus *Lissomphalia* Warén, 1992

Type species: *Lissomphalia bithynoides* (Monterosato, 1880).

Lissomphalia bithynoides (Monterosato 1880) (Fig. 7)

Cyclostrema bithynoides Monterosato, 1880: 66

Anekes sabellii Bogi & Nofroni, 1989: 144.

Lissomphalia bithynoides (Monterosato) – WARÉN (1992: 177-178, figs. 39A-C, 40 A-B).

Material examined: Only one shell with soft parts at 598-610 m. SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600. FRANCE • 3 sh (det. Warén, 1992); off Banyuls, Rech Lacaze; 254-270 m; MNHN.

Type locality: Palermo, Sicily, 190 m.

Lissomphalia bithynoides has a slightly cyrtocoenoid spire with strongly convex

whorls, and was described as sculptured “only” with growth lines inclu-

Figure 5. *Seamountiella azorica* (SE/08 DRN-7). A-C: shell (3.6 mm) and protoconch; D: abapical view of another shell (4.0 mm); E, F: shell (3.4 mm) and its operculum.

Figura 5. *Seamountiella azorica* (SE/08 DRN-7). A-C: concha (3,6 mm) y protoconcha; D: vista abapical de otra concha (4,0 mm); E, F: concha (3,4 mm) y su opérculo.

ding inside the umbilicus. The protoconch with half a whorl, sculptured with 11 strong spiral cords, is highly characteristic and unusual among members of the family.

Despite the generic name, *Lissomphalia bithynoides* actually has a tenuous sculpture inside the umbilicus. We studied three shells from off Banyuls, Mediterranean coast of France, which were listed in the material examined by WARÉN (1992) when he established *Lissomphalia*, and those have a definite microsculpture of minute (ca. 2 µm) granules which tend to be coalescent along irregular lines. This microsculpture is discontinued abruptly along a line delimiting the umbilicus (Figure 7H) and is variable including among

individuals of the same locality (compare Fig. 7G and 7H). The microsculpture may be limited to scarce granules as in WARÉN's (1992) figure 40B, therefore likely to be overlooked. Since we here document the existence of an umbilical microsculpture in Mediterranean specimens, we consider that this character does not support the distinction of more than one species between Galicia and the Mediterranean.

Lissomphalia bithynoides is known from the Gorringe and Josephine banks, southwest Portugal, western Mediterranean and Adriatic Sea, between 90 and 440 m (WARÉN 1992; PEÑAS & GIRIBET, 2003). This finding extends its area of distribution to the north.

Genus *Mikro* Warén, 1996

Type species: *Mikro globulus* Warén, 1996.

Figure 6. *Ganesa nitidiuscula*. A: shell (1.6 mm) (SE/08 DRN-7); B-D: protoconch and detail of its sculpture; E: umbilical cleft; F: shell (1.6 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-15); G: growth lines; H: umbilical cleft.

Figura 6. *Ganesa nitidiuscula*. A: concha (1,6 mm) (SE/08 DRN-7); B-D: protoconcha y detalle de su escultura; E: hendidura umbilical; F: concha (1,6 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-15); G: líneas de crecimiento; H: hendidura umbilical.

Mikro globulus Warén, 1996 (Fig. 8A-F)

Mikro globulus Warén, 1996: 199, figs. 1C-F, 2, 7D, 8D, 10D.

Material examined: Only one empty shell at 908-1106 m. SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Type locality: off southern Iceland, BIOCE 2237 (62°27.00'N - 12°55.00'W), 1099 m.

Mikro globulus is known from off Iceland (WARÉN, 1996), the Rockall Bank (FREIWALD & BECK, 2007) and the South Azorean Seamount Chain (HOFF-

MAN *ET AL.*, 2020), in the depth range 677-1500 m. This species is here recorded for the first time in the Spanish malacofauna.

Figure 7. *Lissomphalia bithynoides*. A: shell (0.72 mm) (DAI/03 EBS-600); B, C: protoconch; D, E: umbilical area and detail of its sculpture (framed area of D); F: shell (0.79 mm) from off Banyuls, Rech Lacaze, 254-270 m; G: umbilical area; H: umbilical area of another shell from the same locality.
 Figura 7. *Lissomphalia bithynoides*. A: concha (0,72 mm) (DAI/03 EBS-600); B, C: protoconcha; D, E: zona umbilical y detalle de su escultura (área enmarcada en D); F: concha (0,79 mm) recolectada frente a Banyuls, Rech Lacaze, 254-270 m; G: zona umbilical; H: zona umbilical de otra concha de la misma localidad.

Mikro minimus (Seguenza G., 1876) (Fig. 8G-L)

Trochus (*Margarita*) *minima* Seguenza, 1876: 186.

Trochus minutulus Jeffreys, 1883: 95, pl. 20 fig. 2.

Lissotesta minima (Seguenza) – WARÉN (1992: 171-172, figs. 25E, F; 29A-C).

Mikro minima (Seguenza) – HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020: 63-64.

Material examined: Eighteen shells (two with soft parts) in five samples between 566 and 1499 m. SPAIN • 2 spc + 7 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598-610- m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 3 sh; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 20 sep. 2003; DIVAARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 4 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 42°45.9'N, 09° 41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIV-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Type locality: Upper Pliocene, Calabria.

Figure 8. A-F: *Mikro globulus* (SE/08 DRN-7). A: shell (1.21 × 0.94 mm); B, C: apical whorls; D: protoconch; E: transition protoconch/teleoconch; F: umbilical area. G-L: *Mikro minimus*. G: shell (1.5 × 1.1 mm) (SE/08 DRN-7C); H, I: shell (0.7 × 0.6 mm) (DAI/08:EBS600) and detail of the umbilicus (framed area); J: microsculpture of the teleoconch (SE/08 DRN-7); K, L: protoconch.

Figura 8. A-F: *Mikro globulus* (SE/08 DRN-7). A: concha (1,21 × 0,94 mm); B, C: vueltas apicales; D: protoconcha; E: transición protoconcha/teleoconcha; F: área umbilical. G-L: *Mikro minimus*. G: concha (1,5 × 1,1 mm) (SE/08 DRN-7C); H, I: concha (0,7 × 0,6 mm) (DAI/08:EBS600) y detalle del ombligo (marco); J: microescultura de la teleoconcha (SE/08 DRN-7); K, L: protoconcha.

Mikro minimus is known from the Rockall Bank (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010), Bay of Biscay, Ibero-Moroccan Gulf (WARÉN, 1992), Canary Islands (ORTEGA

& GOFAS, 2019, misidentified as *Mikro globulus*), and Southern Azorean Seamount Chain (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020), in the depth range 500-2300 m.

Genus *Parviturbo* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945

Type species by original designation: *Parviturbo rehderi* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945

Parviturbo ergasticus Rubio, Rolán & Gofas, 2015 (Fig. 9)

Cyclostrema sphaeroideum (S.V. Wood, 1842): Jeffreys, 1880: 317.

Parviturbo ergasticus Rubio, Rolán & Gofas, 2015: 177-179, fig. 4A-E.

Material examined: Twelve empty shells in 7 samples between 581 and 1106 m. SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°47.188'N, 08°53.053'W to 43°55.312'N, 08°53.101'W; 770-842 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 2 sh; 43°51.774'N, 08°53.640'W to 43°52.516'N, 08°53.478'W; 798- 801 m; 15 sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 4 sh; 43°51.873'N, 08°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 08°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 15 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 2 sh; 43°38.812'N, 09°07.949'W to 43°39.841'N, 09°07.405'W; 999-1001 m; 28 sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 43°20.49'N, 09°34.03'W to 43°21.22'N, 09°32.96'W; 846-771 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-16.

Type locality: Cap Breton Canyon, Bay of Biscay (43°36'N - 01°55'W, 1019 m).

The shells studied showed a high degree of variability regarding the development of the flattened spiral cords and ribs (Fig. 9A, C, E), while the holotype and the shell figured by RUBIO

ET AL. (2015, fig. 4F) presents non-flattened ribs and cords, clearly narrower than their interspaces. *Parviturbo ergasticus* is known from the Bay of Biscay and south of Portugal (RUBIO *ET AL.*, 2015).

DISCUSSION

Although species of Skeneidae are common and widespread in a wide variety of habitats, from shallow coastal waters down to the deep bottoms, and despite the extensive sampling effort, only 128 shells assigned to this family were found, belonging to 11 species. This is probably because these species are tiny and fragile and can be lost during sampling or during the sorting process. Of the species studied only four were found alive: *Skenea basistriata*, *Cirsonella romettensis*, *Seamountiella azorica* and *Mikro minimus*. These last three species were also the most abundant, with 43, 41 and 18 shells, respectively. Only few empty shells of the remaining species were found, and only one shell of three of them (*Lissomphalia bithynoides*, *Mikro globulus* and *Cirsonella aff. gaudryi*).

Skenea serpuloides and *Dikoleps nitens*, were found only on the shelf samples, between 110 and 237 m in depth. The remaining species were found deeper than 400 m depth, but *Cirsonella romettensis*, which was found in the widest bathymetric range, between 230 to 2033 m.

Out of the studied species, only *Cirsonella romettensis* and *Seamountiella azorica* have been recorded in the Galicia Bank (RUBIO *ET AL.*, 2019; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021), a large seamount located close to the studied area about 120 miles off the northwest coast of Galicia.

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Figure 9. *Parviturbo ergasticus*. A: shell ($D=0.97$ mm) (DAI/03 AT-800); B: detail of area framed in A; C: shell (1.3×1.3 mm) (SE/08 DRN-7C); D: shell (0.9×0.9 mm) (DAI/03 AT-800); E: protoconch (same shell as A); F, G: shell (0.98 mm) (DAII/08 DRN-16) and detail of its sculpture; H, I: shell (0.8 mm) (VE/04 DRN-1000) and detail of its sculpture; J, K: shell (1.0 mm) (VE/04 DRN-1000) and detail of its sculpture.

Figura 9. Parviturbo ergasticus. A: concha ($D=0,97$ mm) (DAI/03 AT-800); B: detalle del área enmarcada en A; C: concha ($1,3 \times 1,3$ mm) (SE/08 DRN-7C); D: concha ($0,9 \times 0,9$ mm) (DAI/03 AT-800); E: protoconcha (misma concha que A); F, G: concha ($0,98$ mm) (DAII/08 DRN-16) y detalle de su escultura; H, I: concha ($0,8$ mm) (VE/04 DRN-1000) y detalle de su escultura; J, K: concha ($1,0$ mm) (VE/04 DRN-1000) y detalle de su escultura.

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